

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №5 (19)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 5 (19)

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100, г.
Бухара, ул. Гиждуванская, 23.

Телефон (99865) 223-00-50

Факс (99866) 223-00-50

Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

e-mail baymuradovravshan@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/6
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Мустақиллиги, 70/2.

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APPLICATION OF ADVANCED SOLUTIONS FOR ACETABULAR DEFECT RECONSTRUCTION IN REVISION ORTHOPEDICS**Valiev O.E.¹, Tilyakov Kh.A.²**¹Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics, Tashkent, Uzbekistan²Research Institute of Rehabilitation and Sports Medicine at Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Resume. Large acetabular defects, particularly those associated with pelvic discontinuity, remain one of the most challenging problems in revision total hip arthroplasty (THA). Such defects complicate the fixation of the acetabular component and significantly increase the risk of complications. One of the promising solutions to this issue is the use of custom triflange acetabular components (CTACs), designed on the basis of preoperative computed tomography, taking into account the specific bone defects of each patient. Objective. To perform a clinical and functional assessment of the effectiveness of innovative methods of revision THA in patients with extensive acetabular defects. Materials and methods. The study included 8 patients who underwent revision THA using patient-specific components manufactured with computer modeling and 3D printing technologies. The mean follow-up period was 7 ± 2 months (ranging from 2 to 10 months). According to the W.G. Paprosky classification, 5 patients had type 3B defects, 2 had type 3A defects, and 1 had a type 2C defect. In 6 patients, pelvic bone defects were combined with various femoral lesions. Results. Severe complications were observed in 2 patients (25%): one case of prosthesis dislocation with hematoma formation required repeat surgical debridement, and in another case, recurrent dislocations within a month after surgery necessitated replacement of the acetabular component with a dual-mobility system. In one patient, late postoperative muscle-tonic pain was reported, which was managed conservatively. The mean Harris Hip Score improved from 29 ± 6 preoperatively to 77 ± 8 postoperatively ($p = 0.001$). Pain intensity on the VAS decreased from 7 ± 1 to 3 ± 1 ($p = 0.001$). Conclusions. The use of additive technologies in revision THA for patients with extensive acetabular and pelvic defects allows precise preoperative planning, individualized implant design, restoration of hip biomechanics, and reliable fixation of CTACs. This approach significantly improves clinical outcomes and reduces pain severity in the early postoperative period.

Keywords: revision total hip arthroplasty, acetabular defects, additive technologies, 3D modeling.

РЕВИЗИОН ОРТОПЕДИЯДА ИЛГ 'ОР ЕЧИМЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНГАН ҲОЛДА ҚУЙМИЧ КОСАСИНИНГ ЙИРИК ДЕФЕКТЛАРИНИ ҚОПЛАШ**Валиев О.Э.¹, Тилияков Ҳ.А.²**¹Республика ихтисослаштирилган травматология ва ортопедия илмий-амалий тиббиёт маркази, Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон²Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети қошидаги Реабилитология ва спорт тиббиёти илмий-тадқиқот институти, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Қуймич косасининг катта дефектлари, айниқса чаноқ ҳалқасининг яхлитлиги бузилиши билан кечадиган ҳолларда, сон бўғими ревизион эндопротезлашининг энг жиддий муаммоларидан бири бўлиб қолмоқда. Бундай дефектлар асетабуляр компонентни маҳкамлашда қўшимча қийинчиликлар туғдиради ва асоратлар хавфини сезиларли даражада оширади. Ушбу муаммони ҳал этишининг истиқболли йўналишларидан бири — ҳар бир беморнинг суяк дефектлари хусусиятларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда, олдиндан компьютер томографияси асосида лойиҳалаштириладиган индивидуал асетабуляр компонентлардан (СТАС — Сустом Трифланге Асетабуляр Компонент) фойдаланишидир. Тадқиқот мақсади — қуймич косасининг кенг дефектларига эга бўлган беморларда сон бўғими ревизион эндопротезлашида инновацион усулларнинг самарадорлигини клиник-функционал баҳолаш. Материаллар ва усуллар. Тадқиқотга сон бўғими ревизион эндопротезлаш операцияси ўтказилган ва компьютер моделлаштириш ҳамда 3D-принтер технологияси ёрдамида тайёрланган индивидуал компонентлар қўлланилган 8 нафар бемор киритилди. Кузатув муддати ўртача 7 ± 2 ой (2 ойдан 10 ойгача)ни ташкил этди. W.G. Paprosky классификацияси бўйича 5 беморда 3Б, 2 беморда 3А, 1 беморда 2С турдаги дефектлар аниқланган. 6 нафар беморда чаноқ суяги дефектлари сон суяги шикастланишлари билан бирга кечган. Натижалар. 2 беморда (25%) жиддий асоратлар кузатилди: улардан бирида гематома билан кечган эндопротез чиқиши қайта жарроҳлик аралашувини талаб қилди; бошқасида эса операциядан бир ой ўтиб такрорий чиқишлар сабабли асетабуляр компонент

қўшалок ҳаракатчанлик тизимига алмаштирилди. Яна бир беморда кеч даврда мушак-тоник оғриқлар қайд этилди, улар консерватив даволаш билан бартараф этилди. Харрис шкаласи бўйича ўртача кўрсаткич операциягача 29 ± 6 баллни, операциядан кейин эса 77 ± 8 баллни ташкил этди ($p = 0,001$). VAS бўйича оғриқ интенсивлиги 7 ± 1 баллдан 3 ± 1 баллгача камайди ($p = 0,001$). Хулосалар. Сон бўғими ревизион эндопротезлашида кенг қўймиш косаси дефектларига эга беморларда аддитив технологиялардан фойдаланиш аниқ олдиндан режалаштириш имконини беради, индивидуал конструкцияни танлашни осонлаштиради, сон бўғими биомеханикасини тиклайди ва СТАСнинг ишончли фиксациясини таъминлайди. Бу ёндашув клиник натижаларни сезиларли даражада яхшилайди ва оғриқ синдромини эрта даврларданоқ камайтиришига ёрдам беради.

Калит сўзлар: сон бўғими ревизион эндопротезлаш, қўймиш косаси дефектлари, аддитив технологиялар, 3D-модел.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ПЕРЕДОВЫХ РЕШЕНИЙ ПРИ ЗАМЕЩЕНИИ ДЕФЕКТОВ ВЕРТЛУЖНОЙ ВПАДИНЫ В РЕВИЗИОННОЙ ОРТОПЕДИИ

Валиев О.Э.¹, Тилияков Х.А.²

¹Республиканский специализированный научно-практический медицинский центр травматологии и ортопедии, г. Ташкент, Узбекистан

²Научно - исследовательский институт реабилитологии и спортивной медицины при Самаркандском государственном медицинском университете, г. Самарканд, Узбекистан

Резюме. Значительные дефекты вертлужной впадины, особенно сопровождающиеся нарушением целостности тазового кольца, остаются одной из наиболее серьёзных проблем ревизионного эндопротезирования тазобедренного сустава. Такие дефекты создают дополнительные трудности при фиксации ацетабулярного компонента эндопротеза и существенно повышают риск осложнений. Одним из перспективных решений данной проблемы является применение индивидуальных вертлужных компонентов (СТАС's — Custom Triflange Acetabular Component), проектируемых на основе предоперационной компьютерной томографии с учётом особенностей костных дефектов каждого пациента. Цель исследования — провести клинико-функциональную оценку эффективности применения инновационных методов ревизионного эндопротезирования тазобедренного сустава у пациентов с обширными дефектами вертлужной впадины. Материал и методы. В исследование включены 8 пациентов, перенёвших ревизионное эндопротезирование тазобедренного сустава с использованием индивидуальных компонентов, изготовленных с применением технологий компьютерного моделирования и 3D-печати. Средний срок наблюдения составил 7 ± 2 мес. (от 2 до 10 мес.). По классификации W.G. Paprosky у 5 пациентов выявлены дефекты типа 3B, у 2 — типа 3A, у одного — типа 2C. У 6 пациентов костные дефекты таза сочетались с различными поражениями бедренной кости. Результаты. Серьёзные осложнения отмечены у 2 пациентов (25%): у одного произошёл вывих эндопротеза с формированием гематомы, потребовавший повторной хирургической обработки; у другого через месяц после операции повторяющиеся вывихи потребовали замены ацетабулярного компонента на систему двойной мобильности. В одном случае в позднем послеоперационном периоде выявлены боли мышечно-тонического характера, купированные консервативно. Средний показатель по шкале Харриса составил до операции 29 ± 6 баллов, после — 77 ± 8 баллов ($p = 0,001$). Интенсивность боли по VAS снизилась с 7 ± 1 до 3 ± 1 баллов ($p = 0,001$). Выводы. Использование аддитивных технологий при ревизионном эндопротезировании тазобедренного сустава у пациентов с обширными дефектами вертлужной впадины позволяет провести точное предоперационное планирование, индивидуализировать выбор конструкции, восстановить биомеханику тазобедренного сустава и достичь надёжной фиксации СТАС's. Применение способствует значительному улучшению клинических результатов и снижению выраженности болевого синдрома уже в ранние сроки после операции.

Ключевые слова: ревизионное эндопротезирование тазобедренного сустава, дефекты вертлужной впадины, аддитивные технологии, 3D-модель.

e-mail: Valiev_odil@mail.ru, shaxxas.tilyakov@gmail.com

Introduction. In recent years, there has been a rapid increase in the number of surgical interventions utilizing additive technologies, both in Russian medicine and in global practice. Rapid prototyping and 3D technologies are being applied not only in the production of patient-specific implants but also at the stages of preoperative planning and postoperative monitoring [1,3,5]. According to global statistics, by 2020 the pro-

duction volume of medical devices using additive technologies had increased on average by 60% compared to 2013 [4,5].

The use of additive technologies enables the modeling and fabrication of implants that take into account the patient's anatomical features and the surgeon's preferences, thereby reducing preoperative preparation time and accelerating the manufacturing process. The application of MSCT and MRI makes it possible to work with virtual models, eliminating the need to create physical prototypes [12,15].

One of the key advantages of 3D printing is the ability to define the structure and depth of implant cells at the modeling stage. However, issues concerning the surface structure of implants for the acetabular region remain a matter of debate [6,10,13]. Different approaches to the philosophy of endoprosthetics adopted by manufacturers, as well as restrictions related to intellectual property protection, complicate the development of a unified position. Research findings are contradictory: Zheng Yu [13] points to bone tissue integration into implant surfaces with complex pore geometry, whereas Hara D. [11] and Chen Z. [8] report uneven bone distribution in such constructs.

Of particular interest is the question of the optimal pore size. Most authors [8,12,15] agree that it should be within the range of 400–600 μm when using simple geometric forms. In this regard, studying the osteoconductive properties of implant surfaces with identical geometry but varying pore sizes appears to be especially relevant.

Materials and Methods. Between 2024 and 2025, an analysis was conducted of treatment outcomes in 8 patients with complex acetabular defects who underwent revision total hip arthroplasty (THA) using custom-made CTAC acetabular components manufactured with 3D-printing technology. All patients provided informed consent for the processing and publication of personal data.

For preoperative planning, both conventional radiographs and multislice computed tomography (MSCT) of the pelvis with 0.5 mm slice thickness were utilized. Based on CT data, a three-dimensional pelvic model was generated: bone and cartilage structures were segmented, and noise and artifacts were removed. The model was then prepared for printing and transferred to an FDM-type 3D printer. Polylactide prototypes demonstrated high accuracy (up to 100 μm), which enabled preoperative assessment of the defect volume, degree of bone loss, and planning of bone grafting strategy, including the choice between standard revision constructs and a custom implant.

The fabrication of the custom component was carried out in collaboration with engineers from Novosibirsk. Based on the computer model, the optimal positioning and orientation of the acetabular implant were determined, including restoration of the hip joint rotation center (inclination 40–45°, anteversion 15–20°). The internal diameter of the cup was designed to be ≥ 50 mm, which reduced the risk of prosthetic head dislocation. Using hybrid modeling methods and topological optimization, a digital model was generated with three flanges and screw holes, with the screw direction and length pre-calculated.

Clinical evaluation of revision THA outcomes was performed using the Harris Hip Score (HHS). Patients were assessed preoperatively and at 3 months postoperatively. A total score of 90–100 points was considered excellent hip function, 80–89 good, 70–79 fair, and below 70 poor [16]. Pain intensity was assessed using a 10-point Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) [17].

Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using *Statistica 6.1* software. For descriptive statistics, results are presented as $M \pm SD$, where M is the mean value and SD is the standard deviation. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results. The study included 8 patients with severe acetabular defects who underwent revision total hip arthroplasty (THA) using custom-made acetabular components. The cohort comprised 5 men and 3 women, with a mean age of 63 ± 12 years (range, 39–80 years) and a mean body mass index (BMI) of 27.4 ± 4.8 kg/m^2 (range, 22.0–38.5 kg/m^2). The mean follow-up duration was 7 ± 2 months (range, 2–10 months). Two patients had a history of one previous hip surgery, whereas six had undergone two or more procedures, including spacer removal or implantation, revision arthroplasties, and debridement for infectious complications. The main indications for custom implant use were aseptic loosening with a segmental acetabular defect (3 patients), spacer instability with an analogous defect (4 patients), and iliofemoral nearthrosis following prosthesis removal (1 patient). According to the W.G. Paprosky classification, 5 patients presented with type 3B defects, 2 with type 3A, and 1 with type 2C. In 4 of the 5 patients with type 3B defects, pelvic discontinuity involving both anterior and posterior columns was observed, corresponding to type IV defects under the AAOS classification. Six patients also had associated femoral bone loss (Paprosky type 2 to 3B), and in one case, a Vancouver-classified periprosthetic fracture of the greater trochanter was documented.

The mean time required to design and manufacture a custom implant was 41 ± 6 days. Six procedures were performed via the posterior approach, while two were carried out using modified Kocher-Langenbeck and Harding approaches. In one case, extended trochanteric osteotomy was performed during removal of an

unstable spacer; in another, a two-stage procedure was employed with external fixation followed by THA due to a 7 cm limb shortening and severe joint deformity. All bone defects were managed with auto- and allografts, and the mean acetabular component diameter was 47 ± 2 mm. To prevent dislocation, a dual mobility system with cement fixation was used in 6 patients. Femoral head diameters were 28 mm in 6 cases and 32 mm in 2. The mean operative time was 138 ± 35 minutes (range, 80–190), and intraoperative blood loss ranged from 300 to 1700 ml, with a mean of 570 ± 420 ml.

Postoperative complications occurred in 2 patients (25%). One developed a hematoma and dislocation of the prosthetic head, requiring revision surgery. Another experienced recurrent dislocation, which was managed by replacing the acetabular component with a dual mobility system. In addition, one patient reported pain and motion restriction 9 months after surgery due to a musculoskeletal tonic syndrome following intensive physical activity, which was successfully managed conservatively. Clinical evaluation showed that the mean Harris Hip Score improved from 29 ± 6 points preoperatively to 77 ± 8 points at 3 months postoperatively ($p = 0.001$). Pain intensity on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) decreased from 7 ± 1 to 3 ± 1 ($p = 0.001$). Thus, in the early postoperative period, the use of custom acetabular components resulted in significant functional improvement of the hip joint and marked reduction of pain.

Clinical Case. Patient S., a 68-year-old woman, underwent total hip arthroplasty (THA) of the left hip in 2017 for dysplastic coxarthrosis. In the early postoperative period, she developed a periprosthetic infection that was refractory to conservative treatment. In 2021, at our clinic, the prosthesis was removed, the septic focus was debrided, and a monopolar spacer was implanted. Despite treatment, the patient continued to experience pain, limited joint mobility, thigh muscle weakness, dependence on a cane, and limb shortening of 2.5 cm.

Fig. 1 — Preoperative pelvic radiograph.

In 2022, examination revealed restricted joint mobility and migration of the acetabular component with the formation of a Paprosky type 3B defect and pelvic discontinuity (AAOS type IV), as well as a femoral defect of type 3B. The preoperative Harris Hip Score was 24, and pain intensity on the VAS was 8. At the planning stage, both virtual and physical 3D models of the pelvis were created to assess the defects and select the optimal design for the custom acetabular component.

Fig. 2 — Virtual 3D pelvic model; Fig. 3 — Printed pelvic prototype.

In collaboration with engineers, a titanium implant with a porous surface for improved fixation was designed, featuring recesses for secure cement interdigitation. The sites, number, and orientation of screws were pre-determined based on the 3D pelvic model.

Fig. 4 — Digital model of flange and screw positioning.

Surgery was performed in October 2022 via a posterior approach. The spacer, residual cement mantle, and scar tissue were removed. After distraction of the pelvic discontinuity (W.G. Paprosky technique) and bone grafting of the defects with allografts, the custom implant was placed, providing good primary stability. Subsequent cementation of the acetabular and femoral components was performed. To prevent instability, abductor reconstruction was carried out using the L. Whiteside technique.

Fig. 5 — Implanted cTAC during surgery.

The patient was discharged on postoperative day 8, ambulating with crutches for up to 200 meters with partial weight-bearing. She reported pain reduction, correction of limb malposition, and restoration of equal leg length. At 6 months, the Harris Hip Score improved to 83, and pain on the VAS decreased to 3.

Discussion. According to data from the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics (Tashkent), the need for special revision implants in total hip arthroplasty (THA) arises in approximately 15% of cases. Indications for custom acetabular components may develop even after a single procedure if aggressive surgical techniques were used and resulted in significant bone defects.

Global experience (Berasi, Colen, deBoer, Taunton, et al.) confirms the effectiveness of such reconstructions in patients with catastrophic bone loss and pelvic discontinuity. Reports indicate high implant survival rates and outcomes comparable to those achieved with anti-protrusio cages and augments, although the risk of complications such as dislocation, infection, and component loosening remains. The incidence of dislocation ranges between 17% and 18% across different series.

The main complications are associated with technical challenges, including difficulties in placing large flanges, risks of neurovascular injury, and inaccuracies in acetabular component positioning. Preventive strategies include abductor reconstruction (L. Whiteside technique), dual mobility systems, and the use of locking screws.

Our center's experience also supports the potential of these components. Early results demonstrate high stability even in patients with multiple previous surgeries. The use of 3D modeling and printing enables optimal surgical planning, precise determination of screw size and orientation, and the use of plastic prototypes to safely simulate operative steps.

The main limitations include high cost and prolonged preoperative preparation (several weeks to months). However, economic analyses suggest that the cost of these implants is comparable to that of combining cage systems with augments, while offering superior fixation quality and more predictable outcomes.

Conclusion. Custom-made acetabular components designed with 3D technology represent a promising direction in revision hip arthroplasty for extensive acetabular defects. Their application provides high primary stability, predictable fixation, and significant improvement in hip joint function. The integration of 3D technologies into preoperative planning reduces the risk of complications and optimizes outcomes, even in technically demanding cases.

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For citation: Valiev O.E., Tilyakov Kh.A. Application of advanced solutions for acetabular defect reconstruction in revision orthopedics // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine.* – 2025. – № 5(19). – P. 870–876. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17377427>